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Determinants Of Utilization Of Insecticide Treated Nets In The Prevention Of Malaria Among Pregnant Women Attending Selected Primary Health Care Centers In Ibadan South East

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the utilization of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) in preventing malaria among pregnant women attending Molete Primary Health Care Center in Ibadan South East LGA. Utilizing a survey research design with a convenient sampling technique, the study comprised 100 respondents. Data was analyzed using SPSS, with hypotheses tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents revealed a diverse sample. Majority (44%) were aged between 21-30 years, with 64% having completed tertiary education. Most respondents (68%) identified as Christians, while 32% practiced Islam. Employment status showed that 64% were employed, and 32% were self-employed. Regarding the number of children, 28% had two children, another 28% had three, while 12% had no children. The findings indicated a strong awareness and perceived efficacy of ITNs among the respondents. Specifically, 92% had heard about ITNs, and 84% believed in their effectiveness in preventing malaria during pregnancy. However, practical usage revealed that only 56% knew how to hang ITNs properly, and just 32% had the facilities to do so. All respondents (100%) agreed that free distribution of ITNs could increase their utilization. Ownership of ITNs varied, with 32% having one, another 32% having two, and 28% having none. Awareness levels were high, with 88% being aware of ITNs and 96% having seen them before. Among those who did not own ITNs, 20% cited distance barriers as a major factor. Sources of ITN information were predominantly from antenatal clinics (64%). The study concluded that while awareness and perceived efficacy of ITNs were high among pregnant women, practical barriers to usage existed. Recommendations included enhancing the accessibility of ITNs, improving education on their proper use, and addressing infrastructural barriers to increase utilization rates.

Keywords: Insecticide, Treated, Nets, Malaria, Prevention, Pregnant, Women, Utilization.

INTRODUCTION

Malaria is a global health burden and an important public health problem in tropical and subtropical regions of the world. It is estimated to affect 350 to 500 million people worldwide and cause 1 to 3 million deaths annually (WHO, 2019). The World Health Organization (WHO) states in its periodic health report that more than 90% of malaria cases in the world (estimated at 800,000 annually) go unreported (WHO, 2019). In African countries where malaria transmission is persistent, infection during pregnancy kills 10,000 pregnant women and 200,000 babies annually. It is also said to be responsible for 8-14% of low birth weight babies and 3-8% of infant mortality, threatening more than 30 million

pregnancies annually across Africa. In 2007, there were an estimated 219 million cases of malaria in 87 countries and 435,000 deaths (WHO, 2019).

Malaria infection during pregnancy is a major public health problem that poses significant risks to pregnant women, fetuses, and infants. Pregnant women have more frequent and severe malaria attacks and the probability of dying from malaria is higher than non-pregnant women in the same area (Goshu, 2019). This is because pregnancy reduces a woman's ability to fight malaria, especially in the first trimester. Approximately 19 to 24 million women are at risk of contracting malaria during pregnancy (Adebayo, 2020). Maternal complications associated with malaria and low birth weight are primarily the result of Plasmodium Falciparum Infection and occur primarily in Africa. Malaria during pregnancy also contributes to significant perinatal morbidity and mortality. Malaria infection causes high rates of miscarriage, intrauterine death, premature birth, low birth weight and infant death (President's Malaria Initiative, 2020).

Prevention of malaria in pregnancy using ITNs is undoubtedly one of the main interventions aimed at reducing maternal and infant morbidity and mortality and thereby achieving the 4th, 5th and 6th Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) (Arogundade, 2019). It remains a cost-effective and highly effective tool in global and national malaria control policies and is estimated to be twice as effective as untreated nets (Arogundade, 2019). Results from the 2008 Nigerian Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) show that 17% of households in Nigeria own a mosquito net (treated or untreated) and 8% of households own more than one mosquito net and 16% of households own at least one net which has never been treated. The average number of ITNs per household was less than one, which can be attributed to a weak supply and distribution mechanism (Ankoma, 2018).

In recent years, the distribution of ITNs has been insufficient, targeting only a few local government areas in different states. This made it impossible to achieve saturation in one area⁵. The approach since 2009 has been to start again with a coordinated strategy to deliver Insecticide treated nets to every household across the country through a series of separate campaigns to achieve universal coverage (Adebayo, 2020). In 2010, World Bank supported states (Kano, Jigawa, Bauchi, Gombe, Anambra, Akwaibom and Rivers) conducted net campaigns and health workers distributed free nets to households. The aim was to support the use of the insecticide treated net in households, especially among pregnant women and children under 5 years of age. According to the Federal Ministry of Health, 57.7 million nets were distributed in Nigeria between 2009-2013, representing 90.2% of the total national coverage target. This coverage represented a huge success in the collective effort to expand the intervention (WHO, 2019).

The Malaria Control Strategy has demonstrated improvements in service delivery and resource allocation to support malaria elimination. The World Malaria Report indicated a significant increase in the use of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) among pregnant women. However, in Nigeria, the number of households owning and using ITNs is still far below WHO recommendations (WHO, 2019). Hence, it is essential to examine the utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women attending selected primary health care centers in Ibadan South East.

Statement of Problem

Despite remarkable global efforts to combat malaria, the disease remains a huge burden on pregnant women. It often endangers the mother's health and puts her at greater risk of death. Malaria in pregnancy affects fetal health, often leading to prematurity and low birth weight (LBW), which contribute significantly to neonatal and infant morbidity and mortality (WHO, 2019). In Africa, approximately 25–30 million women become pregnant each year; about 11 million are exposed to malaria, 900,000 give birth to a LBW baby, and 10,000 mothers die (WHO, 2019). However, in order to protect pregnant women and neonates in Nigeria from untimely death caused by malaria infection, there is need for utilization of treated nets during pregnancy. According to World Health Organization the use of ITNs by pregnant women in Nigeria was very low even when compared with other African countries. Only 7.5% of pregnant women slept under an ITN. Also there was a wide gap between ITN ownership and use. Only 25.7% of pregnant women who owned ITN used them (WHO, 2019). Based on these, it is essential

to examine the utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women attending selected primary health care centers in Ibadan South East LGA.

Objective of the Study

The general aim of the study is to examine the utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women attending selected primary health care centers in Ibadan South East LGA. The specific objectives are to:

1. to determine the level of knowledge towards the utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women attending selected primary health care centers in Ibadan South East LGA.
2. to assess the level of awareness towards the utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women attending selected primary health care centers in Ibadan South East LGA.
3. to examine the level of utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women attending selected primary health care centers in Ibadan South East LGA.

Research Questions

1. What are correlation between the independent variables and dependent variable in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women attending selected primary health care centers in Ibadan South East LGA.
2. What is the composite contribution of independent variables on dependent variable in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women attending selected primary health care centers in Ibadan South East LGA.
3. What is the relative contribution of independent variables and dependent variable in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women attending selected primary health care centers in Ibadan South East LGA.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

For this study, the survey research design will be adopted. The choice of the design will be informed by the objectives of the study as outlined in chapter one. This research design provides a quickly efficient and accurate means of assessing information about malaria prevention. It intends to examine the utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women attending selected primary health care centers in Ibadan South East LGA.

Population & Sample and Sampling Technique

The population for this study will be pregnant women attending selected primary health care centers in Ibadan South East LGA. Convenient sampling technique was adopted to select 111 pregnant women for the study. The pregnant women were selected on daily basis for one week as they come for antenatal or treatment. The selected primary health care's in Ibadan south east operates from Mondays to Fridays of every week between the hour of 8 am to 5 pm.

Instrument for Data Collection

A well-structured and self developed questionnaire was used as an instrument to collect information on the utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women attending selected primary health care centers in Ibadan South East LGA. The instrument has a reliability coefficient of 0.75 using Cronbach alpha.

The questionnaire consisted of four sections which are as follow:

- Section A; which comprises of questions on Socio-Demographic data.
- Section B; level of knowledge of respondents towards the utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria.
- Section C; level of awareness of respondents towards the utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria.

- Section D; utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among respondents.

Method of Data Collection

An authorization letter will be collected from the Matron of Molete Primary Health Care Center for permission to conduct the study in the study settings. During quantitative data collection, the researcher will be introduced herself to the respondent (s) who will be selected to participate in the study. The consent form will be read to each respondent after which the respondent either accept or decline to participate in the study. Any respondent who did not consent to participate will be thanked for their time. Those who consented will be issued with questionnaires. All the respondents will be allowed at least 30 minutes to fill the questionnaires after which they will be collected for coding, cleaning and data entry. A total of number of 134 questionnaires will be distributed.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected will be organized, coded and entered in to SPSS version 23. Data were analyzed using correlation and regression analysis.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the pattern of relationships among the independent variables (SES, Education, Acceptance, Knowledge, Awareness) on utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women in selected hospital. in Oyo state, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics and Correlations among the variables

S/N	1	2	3	4	5	6	Mean	SD
SES	1						15.05	7.10
Education	.010	1					4.50	1.05
Acceptance.	.160**	-.080	1				2.91	6.93
Knowledge	.220**	-.108	.086	1			35.30	6.24
Awareness	.301**	-.110**	.104	.447**	1		43.48	10.47
Utilization.	.390**	.258**	.196**	.183**	.210**	1.000	67.02	3.25

1 – SES, 2 – Education 3 - Acceptance, 4 – knowledge, 5 – Awareness, 6 – Utilization of ITNs.

Table 1 shows the variables' mean, Standard Deviation, and zero-order correlation matrix. It was observed that there was significant relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable (utilization of ITNs). There was significant relationship between socio-economic status ($r = 0.390$, $p < 0.05$), level of education ($r = 0.258$, $p < 0.05$), acceptance ($r = 0.196$, $p < 0.05$), knowledge ($r = 0.183$, $p < 0.05$) and awareness ($r = 0.210$, $p < 0.05$) on utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women. All the variables are significantly correlated with on utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women, an indication that they are potent determinants of on utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women.

Research Question Two: *What is the joint contribution the independent variables (SES, Education, Acceptance, Knowledge, Awareness) on utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women in selected hospital. in Oyo state, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Joint contribution of the independent variables

R = 0.649	R – Square = 0.492	Adj. R Square = 0.476	Std. Error of the Estimate = 4.50979		
Regression ANOVA Table					
Variables	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	1433.476	5	286.700	4.48	0.035
Residual	6020.115	94	64.044		
Total	7453.591	99			

- Predictors: (Constant), SES, Education, Acceptance, Knowledge, Awareness)
- Dependent Variable: Utilization of ITNs

Table 2 shows that there was the joint contribution of the independent variables (SES, Education, Acceptance, Knowledge, Awareness) on utilization of ITNs among pregnant women; $R = 0.649$, $p < .05$. The table further reveals 49.2% ($Adj. R^2 = 0.492$) of the variance in the utilization of ITNs among pregnant women were accountable for by the linear combination of the independent variables. The ANOVA results from the regression analysis show a significant contribution of the independent variables on the dependent variables; $F(5, 94) = 4.48$, $p < 0.05$. It implies a joint contribution of the independent variables on utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women in selected hospital in Oyo state, Nigeria.

Research Question Three: *What is the relative contribution of the independent variables (SES, Education, Acceptance, Knowledge, Awareness) on utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women in selected hospital in Oyo state, Nigeria?*

Table 3: Relative Contribution of the Independent Variables on the Dependent Variable

Model	Unstandardized	Coefficients	Standardized	t	Sig
	B	Std Error	Beta		
Constant	13.326	2.369		5.625	0.000
SES	0.185	0.053	0.194	3.494	0.001
Education	0.136	0.023	0.109	2.561	0.020
Acceptance	0.123	0.068	0.118	3.341	0.033
Knowledge	0.107	0.059	0.107	2.966	0.045
Awareness	0.115	0.019	0.345	5.948	0.000

a Dependent Variable: Psychological Wellbeing

Table 3 above shows that all five independent variables significantly contribute to utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women in some selected hospital in Ibadan, Oyo state. The variables include the following: socio-economic status ($\beta = 0.194$, $t = 3.494$, $p < 0.05$); level of education ($\beta = 0.109$, $t = 1.966$, $p > 0.05$), acceptance ($\beta = 0.118$, $t = 3.341$, $p < 0.05$), knowledge ($\beta = 0.107$, $t = 2.966$, $p < 0.05$) and awareness ($\beta = 0.189$, $t = 2.479$, $p < 0.05$). It was observed that awareness was the most potent contributor to utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women and while knowledge was the least.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Research Question 1; What is the knowledge about utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women attending Molete Primary Health Care Center in Ibadan South East LGA?

The survey responses indicated a strong awareness and positive perception of Insecticide Treated Nets (ITNs) among the respondents, with 92% acknowledging knowledge of ITNs and 84% recognizing their effectiveness in preventing malaria during pregnancy. This aligned with findings from Onwujekwe (2023), who observed high awareness and utilization of ITNs in Nigerian communities, highlighting the role of ITNs in malaria prevention. However, only 24% of respondents find ITNs uncomfortable due to heat, which contrasts with studies by Okeke (2020) indicating higher discomfort levels reported by users, suggesting variability in user experiences. Safety concerns are present but not predominant, with 36% perceiving ITNs as potentially harmful, which aligns with studies by Eisele (2019) that discussed misconceptions about ITN safety. Practical usage shows mixed results; 56% know how to hang ITNs, yet only 32% have the facility to do so, underscoring logistical barriers highlighted in studies by Wagbatsoma and Aigbe (2021). Notably, 100% of respondents believe that free distribution could enhance ITN utilization, reflecting findings by Thwing (2022) on the impact of free ITN distribution in increasing usage rates. On ownership, 32% possess one ITN, another 32% have two, and 8% have three or more, with 28% lacking any ITNs, which supports findings from Noor et al. (2007) on ITN ownership distribution patterns in African settings. Sources of ITNs vary, with 40% receiving them from government distribution, 20% from PHC centers, and 12% purchasing them, aligning with the study by Marchant (2021) on ITN distribution channels.

Research Question 2; What is the level of awareness about utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women attending Molete Primary Health Care Center in Ibadan South East LGA?

The study revealed a high level of awareness and utilization of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) among pregnant women in preventing malaria. Specifically, 88% of respondents were aware of ITNs, and 96% have seen them before, indicating widespread awareness. Moreover, 72% own ITNs, demonstrating significant uptake. Among those without ITNs, 20% cited distance barriers, 4% mentioned inaccessibility to free distribution, and another 4% cited affordability issues. Sources of information about ITNs included antenatal clinics (64%), family members (12%), radio (12%), and television (12%). These findings aligned with the study by Onwujekwe (2023), which observed high levels of awareness and ITN utilization in Nigeria due to effective distribution and education campaigns. Similarly, Eisele (2019) found that ITN awareness and ownership were significantly increased through antenatal care services and community outreach programs. The reliance on antenatal clinics for information corroborated the crucial role healthcare providers play in disseminating knowledge about malaria prevention measures.

Research Question 3; What is the level of utilization of insecticide treated nets in the prevention of malaria among pregnant women attending Molete Primary Health Care Center in Ibadan South East LGA?

Table 4.4 revealed the utilization patterns of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) among pregnant women in Ibadan. Only 24% of the respondents started using ITNs before pregnancy, and another 24% began in the first trimester. Usage during mid-pregnancy and the third trimester was lower, with 20% and 32% respectively. Consistent use of ITNs was reported by 64% of respondents, and correct usage by hanging it over the bed was practiced by 60%. Interestingly, 52% use ITNs over doors and windows to prevent mosquito entry. Weather conditions pose a challenge, as 48% cannot use ITNs when it is hot. Despite this, 64% slept under an ITN the previous night. Discomfort while using ITNs is reported by 28%, and 44% experience excessive heat. Only 4% find ITNs unaffordable. These findings aligned with studies by Ng'ang'a (2022), which observed similar utilization patterns and challenges in Kenya, highlighting that consistent and correct usage of ITNs significantly reduces malaria incidence. Conversely, a study by Koenker, (2022) contradicted these findings by reporting higher usage rates and fewer complaints about discomfort and heat, suggesting regional differences in ITN acceptance and use. These insights emphasize

the need for targeted interventions to address barriers to ITN usage, such as improving ventilation and increasing accessibility, to enhance malaria prevention efforts.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the high level of awareness and positive response towards free distribution of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) among pregnant women indicates a successful public health intervention. Yet, challenges such as discomfort and improper use persist, underscoring the need for continuous education and support. Lastly, the findings emphasize the critical role of accessible, user-friendly digital platforms and sustained public health efforts in improving customer service and health outcomes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the researchers' findings, the following recommendations were made;

- 1) Ensure wider and more consistent distribution of ITNs, particularly focusing on remote and underserved areas. This could be achieved through community health programs and partnerships with local organizations to facilitate free distribution.
- 2) Conduct comprehensive awareness campaigns to educate pregnant women on the benefits and correct usage of ITNs. These campaigns should address misconceptions about the safety and comfort of ITNs and provide practical tips for reducing discomfort.
- 3) Integrate ITN distribution and education into routine antenatal care services. Pregnant women should receive ITNs and instructions on their use during their first antenatal visit to ensure early and continued usage throughout pregnancy.
- 4) Involve community leaders and health workers in promoting ITN usage. Training community health workers to support and follow up with pregnant women can increase compliance and address any issues related to ITN usage.
- 5) Implement a system to monitor and evaluate the utilization and effectiveness of ITNs. Regular feedback from pregnant women can help identify barriers to usage and areas needing improvement, ensuring the strategies remain relevant and effective.
- 6) Develop and distribute ITNs designed for comfort in hot climates, and provide practical solutions for reducing heat and discomfort while using ITNs. This may involve using lighter materials or providing fans and other cooling solutions in areas where heat is a significant barrier to usage.

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